

Variable admittance control for hand exoskeletons in virtual reality-based rehabilitation tasks

Alberto Topini^{1,*}, William Sansom¹, Lorenzo Bartalucci¹, Nicola Secciani¹, Benedetto Allotta¹, and Alessandro Ridolfi¹

¹Department of Industrial Engineering, University of Florence, Florence, Italy

*corresponding author: alberto.topini@unifi.it

Abstract—Object manipulation is a crucial element of hand rehabilitation treatments. However, as a standalone process may result in being repetitive and unstimulating. In several studies robotic devices have been proved effective solutions in short and long term therapies for patients with motor dysfunctions and disabilities. Combined with virtual reality-based exercises, Robotics may greatly increase patients involvement, boosting not only the recovery outcome but also psychological aspects like satisfaction and confidence. Moreover, modern physics simulators can render forces from a virtual environment thus providing both visual and force feedback to the user. This work presents the development of a variable admittance control strategy for a rehabilitative hand exoskeleton designed to provide force feedback to the user while interacting with virtual objects in the *Webots* framework. By means of the proposed control, the device can both follow the user's intentions resulting almost transparent to the him/her, and providing a force feedback giving the feeling of handling real objects.

Index Terms—Admittance Control, Rehabilitation Robotics, Hand Exoskeleton, Virtual Reality

I. INTRODUCTION

In the last decades, an increasing number of exoskeletons have been designed and applied in rehabilitation for patients affected by motor dysfunctions and disabilities. Robot-based therapy has proven effective and beneficial for patients, reducing recovery time while increasing results. Besides, therapists can exploit the real-time sensory data to assess progress and tune the exercises accordingly [1].

Since the hand has complex kinematics (27 degrees of freedom) and small size, hand exoskeletons arise among the most challenging robotics devices to develop. A key-role in designing such systems is undoubtedly played by the selection of a convenient control algorithm that detects the user's intention and drives the actuators accordingly. Some of the most widely used strategies involve a combination of a low-level position or force controller — usually a PID or a model-based inverse dynamics controller — and a high-level one that commonly implements an impedance, or admittance model [2].

Impedance and admittance control strategies have the capability to shape the perceived robot's dynamic properties (i.e., inertia, damping and stiffness). This property, which mimics the very workings of the human muscular system, allows to

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simultaneously control both position and contact forces so as to assure a fluid, natural and safe human-robot interaction.

Another fast-growing technology is Virtual Reality (VR), with applications that span from education and tourism to engineering design and surgical training. Its low cost, high flexibility and adaptability make VR a suitable tool for rehabilitation allowing the design of customized and stimulating exercises for patients that have positive psychological effects and, consequently, improve the therapy outcomes [3]. Combining together the strengths of rehabilitation robotics and VR could lead to devices which are cheap, easy to use and capable of straightforwardly and accurately customize therapies.

II. BACKGROUND

The researchers at the Mechatronics and Dynamic Modeling Laboratory (MDM Lab) of the University of Florence have recently developed a remotely-actuated rehabilitative hand exoskeleton in the framework of the Regional research project BMIFOCUS (Fig. 1). A detailed description of the system mechanical architecture, which does represent the basis of the presented research, can be found in [4].

This exoskeleton has been the basis of the presented work. Firstly, a virtual physical twin of the device has been modeled by exploiting the open-source robot simulator *Webots*. Secondly, the overall control system, handling both the virtual and the real exoskeleton, has been developed. Thirdly, the proposed strategy has been tested in a real-time scenario designed to provide the user with the feeling of physically interacting with virtual objects.

Fig. 1. On the left, the hand exoskeleton developed by the MDM Lab researchers in the framework of the BMIFOCUS research project. On the right, the virtual replica modeled in the *Webots* simulator (the purple sphere is added to simulate the interaction with objects).

More specifically, the exoskeleton assists the patient's movements according to force feedback and following a reference force value calculated inside the VR (which renders the digital twin mapping and mimicking the real exoskeleton motion). Whenever the patient grasps a virtual object, the VR changes the reference force value and the HES provides the user with a force feedback as he/she was physically interacting with it.

III. CONTROL SYSTEM

The force-tracking pattern has been achieved by designing a Variable-Admittance Control (V-AC) strategy, which continuously varies the control parameters to best render the force sensation and adapt to the user's motion intentions. Two control levels can be identified. At a higher level the V-AC (described hereafter) takes measurements from the force sensors on the exoskeleton and VR, and generates the references signals for the device inner control loop. At a lower level, the exoskeleton actuators are speed-controlled by means of a PID controller. As a consequence, the V-AC has been realized so as to supply, as output, reference velocities for the motors.

Given the above considerations, the following time-discrete equation for the velocity reference signals has been adopted:

$$v(k) = v(k-1) + \frac{F(k) - F_d(k) - Bv(k-1)}{M} T_s \quad (1)$$

where $v(k)$ represents the speed reference for the PID controller, M and B respectively highlight the inertia and damping terms, $F(k)$ outlines the BMIFOCUS exoskeleton force feedback and $F_d(k)$ constitutes the force reference (supplied by the VR), to be tracked by the overall system.

The variable admittance feature has been achieved by real-time adjusting the inertia and damping terms according to the user's intention so as to actively assist the patient's desired motion and enhance the BMIFOCUS device transparency. More in detail, as long as the intent is accelerating, the damping and inertia default values B and M , both counteracting the motion, are reduced by exploiting a correction factor proportional to the desired acceleration while keeping constant the inertia to damping ratio, as follows:

$$B_{acc} = B - \alpha_{acc} |\ddot{x}_d| \quad (2)$$

$$M_{acc} = M \frac{B_{acc}}{B} \quad (3)$$

On the other hand, whereas decelerating purposes are detected, the damping value should be increased while the inertia still decreased to promptly stop the exoskeleton motion. In order to produce this behavior while avoiding discontinuities on parameter values an exponential function, the following changes to the default values B and M have been adopted [5].

$$B_{dec} = B + \alpha_{dec} |\ddot{x}_d| \quad (4)$$

$$M_{dec} = M_f \frac{B_{dec}}{B} (1 - \beta(1 - e^{-\gamma(B_{dec}-B)})) \quad (5)$$

with β and γ parameters to be accurately tuned for an enhanced smoothness of the whole architecture.

For sake of completeness, human intention detection is achieved by means of a simple heuristic methodology: whereas acceleration and velocity keep the same direction, an acceleration willingness is predicted; conversely, the decelerating desire is inferred.

Fig. 2. Example of patient-VR interaction in a grasping scenario for a single finger. Whenever the user grasps a virtual object, the exerted force (in blue) tracks the reaction force from the virtual environment (in red).

IV. RESULTS AND CONCLUSION

The presented work aimed to design a rehabilitation tool bringing together the benefits of robotic exoskeletons and VR. A digital twin has been built in *Webots* and thoroughly tested for coherence and consistency with the real device.

Turning to a qualitative overview of the achieved results, the V-AC control strategy has highlighted significant performances in terms of force feedback rendering quality and response time. Finally, the interaction between patient and VR has been analyzed. The measured forces show the effectiveness in rendering force feedback thus achieving a noteworthy physical human-robot interaction (Fig. 2).

In conclusion, the developed device does arise as an advanced tool for therapists during hand rehabilitation. Indeed, its flexible structure can be easily adapted to each patient and exercise while adequately preserving safety. The use of a virtual environment can also provide a variety of settings making even repetitive exercises more engaging.

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